

Studies on the Interaction of Lewis Acids with Phenacylidene *p*-Dimethyl Amino Aniline

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Krohnke and Gross¹ observed that *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenyl glyoxal interacts with different Lewis acids (halides of Hg²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Al³⁺) causing bathochromic effect in the absorption spectra of the molecule. Preliminary experiments have shown that the Lewis acids react with the anil in acetonic medium to form coloured complexes which can be crystallised from acetonitrile.

Stock solutions of Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) and Fe(III) halides of A.R (B.D.H) grade were prepared in redistilled acetone. Phenacylidene-*p*-dimethyl amino aniline (m.p. 88°) was synthesised by condensing phenyl glyoxal hydrate² and *p*-amino dimethyl aniline³ (equimolar quantities) in 95% ethanol on a water bath for about 1 hr. The solid mass on crystallisation with ligroin gave reddish yellow plates with bronze like lustre. Its solution was also prepared in acetone.

Instruments, the experimental setup and the procedure were the same as in our previous communication⁴.

Vosburgh and Cooper's method⁵ gave the λ_{max} at 575, 550, 565 and 600 m μ for Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) and Fe(III) complexes respectively indicating the presence of only one complex in each case in acetone medium. The ligand gave the maxima at 475 m μ in acetonic medium. The composition of the interaction products was determined by applying Job's method of continuous variation⁶, slope ratio⁷ and molar ratio methods⁸. Curves of the molar ratio method for iron complex are given in Fig. 1. Similar types of curves were also obtained in other cases. These curves were also used to calculate the stability constants which are given in table I.

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1 : 1 complex was formed in the case of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) and 1 : 2 (M : L) complex in the case of Fe(III).

Fig. 1. Molar ratio plots for the iron complex. Vol. of ligand in ml

Curve (1). Concentration of Ligand = $1.11 \times 10^{-3} M$

Curve (1). Concentration of Fe(III) = $0.36 \times 10^{-3} M$

Curve (2). Concentration of Ligand = $0.90 \times 10^{-3} M$

Curve (2). Concentration of Fe(III) = $0.43 \times 10^{-3} M$

Total volume = 20 ml.

Volume of metal ion = 5 ml.

These complexes were isolated in the solid form by mixing the reactants in the ratio of 1 : 1 for Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complex and 1 : 2 for Fe(III) complex. The mixture was dried in a vacuum desiccator and the solid so obtained was then recrystallised from acetonitrile.

TABLE 1

*Composition and stability of the metal complexes of phenacylidene
p-dimethyl amino aniline*

Chelate	Ratio M : L	Stability constant K	ΔF K.Cals/mole
<i>p</i> -Zn(II)	1 : 1	1.1×10^5	- 6.8
<i>p</i> -Cd(II)	1 : 1	3.5×10^5	- 7.6
<i>p</i> -Hg(II)	1 : 1	6.4×10^3	- 5.2
<i>p</i> -Fe(III)	1 : 2	1.01×10^{12}	-16.50

These complexes were chemically analysed by determining their metal content. The results are given in table 2.

